

Machine learning analysis of the T cell receptor repertoire identifies sequence features that predict self-reactivity: data analysis plan for validation analyses

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Summary

We recently conducted an exploratory analysis of murine T cell receptor (TCR) repertoire data.¹ Specifically, we analyzed the complement-determining region 3 (CDR3) of the TCR β chain from naïve CD4⁺ T cell populations that express high or low levels of the surface marker CD5 (CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} cells). This document describes in advance a series of analyses we will conduct on a held-out validation dataset from 10 mice to confirm the hypotheses derived from our exploratory analysis. We are providing this document in the interest of transparency.

Hypotheses

Our exploratory analysis generated the following specific hypotheses on features that could predict whether a naïve conventional CD4⁺ cell with a given CDR3 β sequence is CD5^{lo} or CD5^{hi} (see Figure 4 of Textor *et al.*¹):

1. CDR3 β sequences with a larger amount of non-templated nucleotide insertions are associated with CD5^{lo} status.
2. CDR3 β sequences containing the gene segments V14, V20, or J1-2 are associated with CD5^{lo} status.
3. CDR3 β sequences containing glutamic or aspartic acid in the middle positions are associated with CD5^{lo} status.
4. CDR3 β sequences containing the gene segments V2, V3, V12-1, V12-2, or V15 are associated with CD5^{hi} status.
5. CDR3 β sequences containing the strongly hydrophobic amino acids leucine, isoleucine, valine or phenylalanine in the middle positions are associated with CD5^{hi} status.

We base these hypotheses on the results shown in Figure 4 of our preprint.¹ For the V and J genes, we picked a number of the most salient differences between CD5^{lo} cells CD5^{hi} (Figure 4D); the hypotheses on hydrophobic and acidic amino acids are based on our analysis of length 12 sequences (Figure 4F). We define the “middle positions” as all positions in the junction sequence except for the initial 3 and the final 2 positions. Consequently, hypotheses 3 and 5 only apply for sequences length 6 or longer.

Observables

To quantitatively test the hypotheses above, we define the following features for each sequence:

1. Distance between V and J gene (1 nonnegative integer).
2. Presence of V14, V20, or J1-2 (3 binary variables).
3. Fraction of amino acids in the middle positions that are glutamic or aspartic acid (1 number in the range [0,1]).
4. Presence of V2, V3, V12-1, V12-2, or V15 (5 binary variables).
5. Fraction of amino acids in the middle positions that are leucine, isoleucine, valine or phenylalanine (1 number in the range [0,1]).

For feature 1, we use the V-J distance instead of attempting to estimate the non-templated nucleotide insertions because such insertion comes with substantial uncertainty and increases the noise. In our data exploration, we were able to detect a (tiny) difference between CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} cells with respect to V-J distance but not with respect to non-templated nucleotide insertions.

Features 3 and 5 are similarly defined in previous studies, e.g., other authors have defined a “hydrophobicity index” as the fraction of hydrophobic amino acids in a sequence.^{2,3} We defined the list of strongly hydrophobic amino acids based on the IMGT standard;⁴ specifically, we used the 4 amino acids with the highest hydrophobicity scores.

Data

Exploration dataset (A)

The hypotheses described above were derived from our exploratory analyses on data from 19 mice, with separate CD5^{hi}- and CD5^{lo}-sorted samples for each mouse (38 samples total; see Figure 1B of our preprint¹). We will refer to this as our “exploration dataset (A)”. Sequences in this dataset were further divided into “training data (A1)” (used to train the machine learning model), and “testing data (A2)” (used to evaluate the model). For details on how this split was performed, see Figure 3A and the methods in our preprint;¹ but note that this procedure yields separate training and testing subsets for each sample, and that not all data in A is used in A1 or A2.

Validation dataset (B)

After preliminary analyses on dataset A, we generated a separate “validation dataset (B)” consisting of CD5^{lo}- and CD5^{hi} samples of 10 mice (20 samples total). The sample size of 10 mice was based on the preliminary analyses, from which we estimated that a sample size of 10 should be sufficient to detect differences of the same magnitudes, or slightly lower ones, that we report in our preprint.¹ Aside from preprocessing (described below), the validation set B was held back from the exploratory analysis and has not yet been analyzed at the time of writing.

We will perform our validation analyses using the entire dataset B; we will not remove sequences that are shared between datasets A and B, as the aim of the validation analysis is to determine whether our conclusions drawn from the exploration dataset A generalize to a new set of mice, and many CDR3 β sequences are expected to be found in multiple mice.

Preprocessing

We preprocessed the raw sequencing reads of datasets A and B simultaneously to obtain mapped CDR3 β junction sequences, merging paired-end reads with PEAR⁵ and running the Recover TCR pipeline.⁶ For transparency, we publish the resulting mapped sequences from each CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} sample together with this data analysis plan, which will allow reproducing the analyses described here. To verify that our data processing was successful, we determined the number of mapped reads and sequences for each sample, which was comparable for datasets A and B. Beyond this quality control, we did not perform any further analyses on dataset B; specifically, we did not look at the sequences themselves.

Analysis

Data visualization

First, we will generate a multi-dimensional scaling (MDS) display of dataset B in the same way as done for dataset A in Figure 1E of the published preprint. That is, we will construct a 20x20 distance matrix $M_{ij} = 1 - J(i, j)$, where $J(i, j)$ is the Jaccard index (intersection divided by union) of the two samples being compared. When computing the Jaccard index, we will consider two sequences identical if they have the same mapped V gene, mapped J gene, and amino acid junction sequence. This initial step will be performed to visualize the overall similarity structure between the samples. We expect the samples of the CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} populations to roughly separate into two different clusters; if this is not the case, we will not change our further analyses, but this information will help us to interpret the results of the analyses (for example, it will help us detect outliers, which might reduce the statistical power of the tests defined below).

We will then go on to test the hypotheses 1-5 specified above in two different ways.

Comparing ML-filtered sequence datasets

First, we will use our machine learning (ML) algorithm (already trained on dataset A1) as a filter in the same way as described in our preprint.¹ Specifically, the trained ML model will be used to identify the “confidently predicted” subsets of sequences from the CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} samples of dataset B. We will then average each of the 5 groups of observables described above across each sample (i.e., the coCD5^{lo} and coCD5^{hi} subsets of each mouse). For the observables consisting of multiple binary variables (observable 2 and observable 4), we will compute the logical “or” of these variables per sequence. This procedure will generate 5 numbers for each sample.

We will then use a two-tailed paired T test to determine whether there is a significant difference between coCD5^{lo} and coCD5^{hi} sequences for each of the 5 numbers. The p-values of the 5 paired T tests will be corrected for multiple testing using the Bonferroni method.

This first set of tests will determine to what extent our observations made in our preprint¹ generalize to a new dataset. For illustration, **Figure 1A** shows the result of this set of tests on the exploration dataset A.

Figure 1: Logistic regression model for predicting CD5 status, fitted and evaluated on the exploration dataset. (A) Evaluation of sequence features on dataset A, after using our ML algorithm to filter the 15% most confidently predicted CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} sequences from each sample. P-values: two-tailed paired T test, Bonferroni correction for 5 tests. **(B)** Predicted log-odds ratio (CD5^{hi} vs CD5^{lo}) for all testing sequences (from dataset A2, 20% of dataset A as defined in our preprint¹) split by CD5 status, when using a logistic regression model fitted to 50,000 randomly drawn CDR3 β sequences each for the CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} samples from dataset A1 (Table 1). **(C)** Mean predicted log-odds ratio per sample compared between CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} mice; p-value: paired two-tailed t test. **(D)** Coefficients and 95% confidence intervals of a logistic regression model fitted to a standardized version of the training data. For facilitating comparison between coefficients, the variables “acidity”, “hydrophobicity” and “V-J distance” were transformed to standard deviation 1 before fitting the model in this panel, which is meant to illustrate the relative importance of each observable.

Predicting CD5 status based on the features alone

The second aim of this confirmatory analysis is to see if the identified features can predict CD5 status by themselves, without the filtering by ML. To this end, we have fitted a logistic regression model (Table 1) on 100,000 randomly drawn sequences of the exploration dataset (i.e., 50,000 CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} sequences from dataset A1, where this time we did *not* filter for the coCD5^{hi} and coCD5^{lo} subsets in order to see the predictive value of these features alone). When evaluated on the exploration test set A2, this logistic regression model appears able to distinguish the CD5^{lo} from the CD5^{hi} sequences to some extent (Figure 1B; better than random, but worse than the full ML model described in our preprint¹).

We will run this fitted logistic regression model (Table 1) on all sequences found in each of the 20 samples of dataset B, and determine the average predicted log odds-ratio for being CD5^{hi} per sample. We will then use a two-tailed paired T test to determine whether the predictions differ between CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} samples. Figure 1C shows the results of this analysis on the exploration test set A2; the validation will be performed by applying the same code to dataset B.

This second test will determine whether the features we identified to be associated with confident ML predictions are by themselves able to predict CD5 status, without using the ML algorithm as a filter. We chose to perform this test based on a joint model of all features, rather than each of the individual features, because we expect the differences in each feature to be small due to the considerable overlap between CD5^{lo} and CD5^{hi} sequences, as we show in Figure 2 of our preprint.¹

Code

Code for performing the analyses planned here is published alongside this data analysis plan. The published code loads data from the exploration dataset; for performing the validation analyses, the data being loaded needs to be modified accordingly. The machine learning models used to generate predictions of CD5 status, as well as the fitted logistic regression model of the combined features, is also published alongside this data analysis plan.

	Coefficient	95% CI
(Intercept)	0.1885	[0.1334; 0.2435]
V-J distance	-0.0060	[-0.0096; -0.0024]
V2	0.6208	[0.5618; 0.6798]
V3	0.3863	[0.3400; 0.4327]
V12-1	0.6932	[0.5502; 0.8362]
V12-2	0.7789	[0.6970; 0.8608]
V14	-0.6174	[-0.6897; -0.5452]
V15	0.3895	[0.3348; 0.4441]
V20	-0.2734	[-0.3445; -0.2024]
J1-2	-0.2393	[-0.2967; -0.1818]
hydrophobicity	0.7392	[0.5961; 0.8824]
acidity	-3.1922	[-3.4312; -2.9531]
N	100000	

Table 1: Coefficients of our fitted logistic regression model. Created using the R package “texreg”.⁷

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